

TRUANCY: The Concept, Causes, Types, Implications and intervention Strategies for Students with Truancy.

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Abstract

Truancy among students become a growing problem. The truancy problem has been manifested in different forms. Some students deliberately refuse to attend the full days of school, some students may attend school but run away after break, while some students arrive at school after break. Likewise, there are some students who attend school and stay in the class for lessons that they have interest in but intentionally refuse to stay in class for lessons that they do not have interest in due the teacher's hostile attitude or hatred of the subject. Also, there are some students who attend school but do not go to their classes at all. Therefore, this paper explained the concept of truancy, causes, types, implications and intervention strategies for students with truancy. Lastly, conclusion and recommendations were provided.

Keywords: Truancy, Students, Implications, Management.

Introduction

According to Smith (2007), behavior disorders are divided into two broad categories which include: internalizing behavior problems and externalizing behavior problems. The internalizing behavior problems are those behavior disorders that are typically manifested inwardly by the students which include anxiety disorder, depressive disorder, withdrawal tendency, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and so on. Meanwhile, the externalizing behavior problems are those behavior disorders that have been manifested outwardly by the students which include aggressive disorder, defiant disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, conduct disorder, truancy, stealing tendency, among others. Although, students with externalizing behavior problems are those whom teachers are more likely to refer for appropriate supervision and special treatment. While, students

with internalizing behavior problems are often at just as much at risk for school failure if care is not properly taken.

Truancy is one of the externalized behavior disorders; a problem which seriously and negatively affects students schooling in particular and their life progress in general (Bulama & Bosede, 2016). Huizinga (2005) considers truancy as a deliberate absence from school on the part of students without the knowledge and consent of parents, absence of the students from the school for which no reasonable or acceptable excuse is given to school authority. Michael (2007) explained that truancy poses a serious and negative impact on students' academic performance bearing in mind that the strong menace of truancy pervades the entire educational system especially the secondary education system. Truancy among junior secondary school students jeopardizes chances of achieving their educational goals. Globally, truancy among the students has been identified as one of the most prevalent rates that become a predictor of delinquency and indiscipline, and other anti-social behaviors among the students. This becomes detrimental to students' academic achievement in school, class promotion, and graduation.

Various factors are responsible for the causes of truancy among junior secondary school students. Romero (2008) identified the poor school environmental condition, anxiety, school phobia, parental attitude, family poverty as causal factors for truancy among students. Furthermore, Ubogu & Wither (2004) reports that school disciplinary practices, bullying, teacher's hostile attitude, and peer group influence are the reasons why some students become truant. Similarly, shortcomings of teaching, disengagement in school experiences, inadequate teachers both in quantity and quality, lack of infrastructural facilities for quality education are potential factors for truancy among the students (Obanya, 2010). Likewise, Maliki (2013) stated that truancy can be caused by long distances from school which tempt or force the students to withdraw prematurely from school. Truancy is any intentional unauthorized or illegal absence from routine schooling. It may also refer to students who attend school but do not go to classes. Truancy is non-school attendance behavior. It is an irregular attendance of school. Truancy is a delinquent and anti-social behavior which has been caused by many factors like family negligence, school harsh punishment, peer group influence, among others (Huizinga, 2005).

Concept of Truancy

Truancy has been conceptualized from different perspectives of different scholars. Truancy means staying away from school without permission of parents and school authority by students. According to Maynard (2014), truancy is defined as a “deliberate absence from school without parental knowledge”. In the same vein, Farrington (2002) said that truancy is “when a student stays away without permission. A student who absents himself/herself from school without permission from school and home is a truant. Fowowe (2011) observed that irregular school attendance is interchangeably used with truancy which occurs when students fail to attend school without permission from school. Similarly, Nwankwo (2006) stated that truancy among students is abnormal and results to absenteeism. Herbert (2005) stressed that truants lack skills to maintain friendships hence they are isolated by peers. Truancy may refer to students who attend school but do not go to classes. Heilbrun (2003) observed that truancy is practiced by some students who fail to attend school, rather prefer to be with their friends. Globally, truancy is regarded as a cankerworm that has caused set back and deficiency for attainment of viable educational pursuit by secondary school students. Truancy is one of the externalized behavior disorders which seriously and negatively affects students’ educational progress in schools (Animasahun, 2008).

Likewise, Huizinga (2005) considers truancy as a deliberate absence from school on the part of students without the knowledge and permission of parents, absence of the students from the for which no reasonable or acceptable excuse is given. Collins (2010) conceptualizes truancy as students who have been registered in a school but identified as not attending school as the law says they should. Students who are truant typically spend time out of school, away from their homes and tend to conceal their absence from their parents. Many students are absent from school for no legitimate reason.

Truancy among students has been opined as the act of absencing oneself from school without a legitimate reason and without the permission of the parents or the school authorities (Herbert, 2005). It has attracted interest in public discussion as well as in educational research. Since school attendance is of necessity and very important for academic success and moral development of learners. Truancy can mar the potential educational attainment of learners as well as other benefits of educational setting. There is no doubt that the issue of students’ truancy in Nigeria’s school system has attained an alarming proportion. It has been a great concern to the parents, school authorities, teachers, educational practitioners and the government.

This isolated incident (truancy) is quite typical and likely to create problems, which can lead to a varied set of negative and more dangerous consequences and eventually lead to poor academic performance. Although truancy has known effects in individuals, it also has negative effect on the overall learning environment. Indeed, truancy is a great problem for stakeholders and parents as truant students create problems for parents, school and the society at large. Continuous absenteeism from school leads to serious undesirable consequences both for children exhibiting truancy and for the communities (Omojuwa & Uguma, 2003).

Types of Truancy

Ezeani (2006) categorized truancy into three types, which are habitual truancy, occasional truancy, and causal truancy.

1- Habitual Truancy:— it is regarded as specific number of consecutive unexcused absences from school without the knowledge or consent of parents and school authority. It occurs when a student (truant) constantly and continuously is been absent from school without the due knowledge or consent of his parents and school authority. It refers to mainly those students who miss numerous full days of school academic activities.

2- Occasional Truancy:— it occurs when a student does not constantly and continuously absent himself/herself from school, it is irregular non attendance of school. It is when a student kept at home to help take care of his/her younger brother/sister. That is, it is when a student is absent from school with the consent of parents either to help the family and not regular.

3- Casual Truancy:— this type of truancy occurs when student's absence from school is by chance and not regular. For instance, the student who remained lurking with sound of the school bell so that he/she could attend those lesson, interested him/her. That is, students tend to attend the lessons that they are interested.

Causes of Truancy

According to Zhang, Katsiyannis, Barrett, and Wilson (2007), the causes of truancy among the students can be positioned within four major categories. These categories include family factors, school factors, peer group factors, and student factors.

1- Family/Home Factors:- Generally, it is obvious that truancy is a problem that has many causative agents and homes, of the students is regarded as one. The home of the child seriously

contributes to his engagement in truancy. For instance, in a home where there is poverty, lack of concern on the child's education, child abuse, alcohol abuse and other improper ways of child upbringing can easily make him indulge in truancy. Hopskins (2011) and Maduabuchi (2013), were of the opinion that lack of parental guidance, poverty, drug and alcohol abuse, lack of family support, domestic problems, broken homes, family commitments including care duties in the home are some of the factors that make children engage in truant behavior. Musa (2014), opined that children who are not adequately monitored by their parents may show a variety of unhealthy symptoms in behaviours. Adebisi (2017), opines that broken homes is a factor that causes truancy and absenteeism in children because in most broken home there is no proper care for the child.

2- School Factors:- The school is expected to provide conducive atmosphere for proper learning and teaching as well as serving as a place to be loved by the students. However, in some situations school assists in making students to engage in truancy. For instance, in a situation where a school is having teachers who are harsh to students, where there is high level of bullying, un-conducive school environment, harsh punishment, poor management, poor relations with teachers and in some cases irrelevance of the curriculum, then there must be high tendency of truancy from the students (Heilbbrun, 2003). Similarly, Raid (2006), has the view that harsh teachers, negative school experiences such as bullying, boring and boredom classes, un-conducive school environment, indiscipline prevalent in the school, lack of interesting and co-curricular activities are some of causes of truancy among students that come from the school itself.

3- Peer Group Factors:- Peer group is another factor that can influence truancy. According to Ezewu (2010), peer groups are person of same age group, friends or equals with whom the child shares certain social characteristics. This social world to which they belongs could be one in which they share same language, values, norms and mode of interaction which may not be understood by the adults. However, it is through the peer pressure that students are most likely to be introduced and involved in truant behaviours such as drinking, smoking, indecent act and drop out of school.

4- Student Factors:- Some causes of truancy among students really come from the students themselves. For instance, low level of intelligence, peer influences; weak physical health, social and emotional as well as maladjustment do make students engage in truancy (Raid, 2006). Likewise, Hopskins (2011) was of the opinion that student's need to catch up on homework or assessment tasks, illness, lack of social competence, mental health difficulties and physical health, lack of self esteem, social skills and confidence; poor peer relations, lack of academic ability are

some of the causes of truancy mainly coming from the student themselves. Also, Omoegun (2014) Musa was of the view that a child would rather prefer to spend most of his days in the midst of his peers where he would be happier and more relaxed and this gives room for undue peer influence particularly in antisocial behaviours like truancy.

Implications of Truancy

Henry (2007) indicates that truancy's implications are extensive, resulting in negative consequences for multiple levels of society. In the short-term implications, truancy can bring about maladjustment, poor academic performance, school dropout, substance abuse, delinquency, and teen-age pregnancy. In the long-term implications, evidence reveals truancy as a predictor of poor adult outcomes, including violence, marital instability, job instability, adult criminality, and incarceration. Moreover, truancy exerts a negative effect on community because of its correlation with delinquency, crime, and other negative adult outcomes.

Student dropout from school is the most obvious result of chronic truancy. According to Rodriguez and Conchas (2009), truancy and dropout rates are concentrated and worsening in racially segregated central cities in primarily large high schools attended by mostly low-income youth of color. Drop out rates in these areas are at twice the national average, nearly 20%, and exceed 50-60% in some areas of the Nigeria. In these areas, more students are dropping out than graduating. What does this say about our society? What is in store for these students? How do these individuals survive in a country where average income is directly correlated with level of education?

Truancy has many negative and adverse effects on the truants and the society at large. It has been clearly identified as one of the early warning signs that the youth is heading for potential delinquent activity, social isolation and educational failure. Several studies have established lack of commitment to school as a risk factor for substance abuse, delinquency teenage pregnancy and dropping out of school. Bell, Rosen and Dynlacht (2010) have shown that decades of research have identified a link between truancy and later problems in life such as violent crimes, marital problems, adult criminality and incarceration. Truancy has social and financial impact on the truant youths. Academically they make low grades and achieve little educationally. They usually drop out of school resulting in high dropout rates which is inimical to functional education for values knowledge, skills and national development. Other negative consequences of dropping out of

school occasioned by truancy include little employment prospects, lower salaries if employed, but often times not employed or under employed. Truant school dropouts are more likely to depend on their parents' or relatives' good will for survival.

Other consequences of truancy and dropout are less educated work force as youths who are the future leaders become uneducated as a result of truancy and dropping out of school. This will obviously have adverse effect on the nation's workforce and hence low productivity. This will as well increase unemployment and the illiteracy level of the nation. In a situation whereby educational institution of different levels turn out graduates of different cadres annually and push them into the labour market what chances have the truants/dropouts. The above situation will adversely effect the nation's development since employment and literacy levels are among the indices for determining national development (Olley, 2018).

From the foregoing, it could be established that truancy as social vice has numerous negative effects on both the truants and society. On the part of the truants the act makes them school dropouts, uneducated unemployable, security risks and replete with anti-social behaviours. The society on the other hand is not better for it as the truants/school dropouts make no meaningful contribution to the growth and progress of the society. They engage in numerous anti-social behaviours such as smoking, illicit sex, alcoholism, armed robbery, kidnapping and even social interest especially as they are vulnerable to manipulation by the elites especially politicians and evil minded numbers of the society to satisfy their insatiable quest for power and wealth (Bell, Rosen & Dynlacht, 2010).

Intervention strategies for Students with Truancy

There are a considerable number of strategies of intervention that have been employed to combat truancy. Zhang (2007) recommends instructional, behavioral, and community based interventions, and has advocated for a program titled Check and Connect, while Henry (2007) supports the family and instructional intervention approaches. Desocio (2007) initiated a mentor intervention program whereas Reid (2006) investigated a five-tiered intervention approach titled School Based Scheme (SBS) piloted in the United Kingdom (UK). Each of the afore-mentioned strategies and interventions have exhibited at least minimal success within the schools they were initiated. Some of the strategies of intervention include the following:

1- Direct Instruction:- or an instructional approach that places an emphasis on the drill and practice technique throughout scripted, rehearsed, and fast-paced lessons, is a key phrase used in instructional intervention. This is especially useful in reading and math classes where students can receive immediate feedback. Furthermore, teacher praise and reinforcement has empirical support for increasing on-task behavior and decreasing inappropriate behaviors (Zhang, 2007). Through instructional intervention, habitually absent students are encouraged to attend school through praise. However, do not believe that the instructional intervention approach will be enough in and of itself to eliminate, or at the very least decrease chronic unexcused absenteeism. Nevertheless, the strategy elicits empirical support for increasing ontask behavior; therefore, direct instruction could be one component used in the fight against truancy.

2- Positive Behavior Support (PBS):- and or Functional Behavior Assessment (FBA) are two examples of behavioral based interventions. Positive Behavior Support incorporates several empirically proven practices into a continuum of supports for students with challenging behaviors and these supports can either be universal and school wide or more intensely focused on the individual (Zhang, 2007). Functional Behavior Assessment is an example of a more individual based intervention, and is a process in which information is gathered about the function of the student's behavior. This can be used to maximize the effectiveness and efficiency of the student's behavioral support(s) and self-management. This process generally involves self-monitoring, self-evaluation, and positive reinforcement. Moreover, this process is intended to teach students to take responsibility for their social behavior and academic performance. The PBS and FBA also provide a paper trail needed to prove that steps have been taken in an attempt to improve student behavior, and more specifically in this case, student attendance.

3- Abolish Chronic Truancy Now (ACT Now) and Truancy Reduction Demonstration Program (TRDP):- these are two popular community- based interventions. These programs build on the strengths and resources in local communities to target truancy and offer incentives to students and their families for attending school. These community-based interventions include mentoring, intensive family interventions, case management or diversion programs, welfare restrictions as an economic sanction, and expanding police authority (Zhang, 2007). Zhang states that attendance improves when students are given awards, communication with families is strong, parents are assigned a contact person at school, and after school programs are made available to students. However, it becomes obvious that if the entire community is not involved (e.g. parents,

educators, law enforcement, juvenile and family court judges, social services, etc), the program will not be successful in preventing, decreasing, or eliminating truancy. Still, it is of value to provide the community with an opportunity to become invested in its youth and the school's fight against truancy.

4- Check and Connect:- it is a truancy prevention and intervention model that was developed to encourage middle school students that were at risk for dropping out of school to remain engaged in school and on track to graduate (Zhang, 2007). In this model, an assigned individual monitors student levels of engagement on a daily basis using multiple risk factors such as tardiness, skipping classes, absenteeism, behavior referrals, detention, suspensions, grades, and accrued credits. This assigned individual is responsible for ensuring that a student is actually connecting with the school and is indeed participating in the learning environment. This is the Check aspect of the program. In the Connect portion of the program, the assigned individual uses the indicators mentioned above to connect the at risk student to either basic or more intense interventions. The basic interventions include sharing general information about the monitoring system with the student, providing regular feedback to the student about his progress in school, regularly discussing staying in school and its associated benefits, and problem solving strategies that can be used to examine the potential risk factors that the student may be exhibiting. An example of a more intensive based intervention would be that of the FBA, which was discussed earlier. This program would be excellent for chronically absent students because it allows for the fostering of an adult-student relationship based on human interactions and connections. It allows for the student to make a commitment not only to himself, but also to a fellow human being.

Conclusion

The school environment is organized to shape a student's learning behaviour. However, one of the problems associated with schooling is truancy which is a source of concern to the parents and the school authority. Truancy has been identified as a challenge among students in schools globally and in Nigeria in particular. Truancy is a student's deliberate irregular attendance at school. Truancy among students includes lateness to school and class, leaving school before closing time, loitering, dodging lessons and absenteeism.

It is worrisome to note that students tend to face a lot of emotional and psychological problems arising from irregular school attendance, lack of personal and

interpersonal skills to cope with school work. Truant students have negative perception about schooling because it interferes with their freedom as they prefer to spend most of their time with friends. From our cultural perspective when a child fails to attend school, the parents are usually blamed. However, many students struggle with personal issues that relate to lack of personal, interpersonal and problem solving skills, which manifest as behavioural problems that could most likely result to truancy.

Truant students suffer from deprivation, isolation, rejection and unassertiveness, which is due to their inability to cope with social, cognitive and problems-solving skills. Some of them are bullied hence they decide to be absent from school unknown to their parents and the school authority. In addition, some parents neither assist their children in the homework or assignment nor participate in the school programmes. Such parents do not monitor the progress of their children thereby abdicate their responsibility to the school. Also, some students may not have writing materials such as textbooks, pencil, biros, school bags and sandals, hence prefer to be outside while the lessons are going on. Such students' cannot benefit from the various programmes that the school offers. In addition, the effects of truancy include low achievements, criminal and delinquent activities. Truancy is also a clog in the wheel of progress during the teaching and learning, as the teacher has to contend with adequate class management. Thus, management of truancy among students has become imperative. Management of truancy involves the use of adequate counselling intervention to modify the challenges that confront students. Management of truancy provides students with skills for inter-personal relationship and selfmanagement.

Recommendations

1. Regular register attendance check up by form master and follow up by school head in order to minimize the prevalence rates of truancy among the students.
2. The learning environment should be made more active, lively and interesting for the students in order to make them feel comfortable while in school. Also, teachers should be friendly and role models by so doing their negative attitudes towards students will be eliminated. Likewise, parents should supervise their children and equip them with the necessary educational materials to avoid unnecessary excuses from students on why they engage in truant behaviours.

3. Guidance and counseling should be made top priority in secondary schools. Counselors should invite students who engage in truancy for discussions and advice.

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